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WHY DO LEARNERS STRUGGLE TO USE THE LANGUAGE EFFECTIVELY IN REAL-LIFE SITUATIONS?

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the influences contributing to learners' difficulties in using the target language, with a particular importance on speaking skills. Additionally, it investigates whether interactive teaching methods, including role play and debate, enhance learners' communicative competence. The research employed a survey-based method with 8th-grade students as participants. Initially, a questionnaire was administered to identify primary challenges in speaking, including hesitation, limited vocabulary, and low confidence. Based on survey results, targeted classroom activities were designed and implemented. These included role-play tasks and debate sessions, which encouraged students to use the language in meaningful and real-life situations actively. The activities were carried out over a specific period to observe changes in students' speaking performance.

Keywords: communication, speaking skills, fluency, real-life situations, challenges, learners, questionnaire and interview, role play and debate, role play, debate, fluency, hesitation, shyness, peers, self- confidence.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu tadqiqot o'quvchilarning maqsadli tildan foydalanishdagi qiyinchiliklariga ta'sir etuvchi ta'sirlarni tahlil qilishga qaratilgan bo'lib, nutq ko'nikmalariga alohida ahamiyat beradi. Bundan tashqari, interfaol o'qitish usullari, jumladan, rolli o'yin va bahs-munozaralar o'quvchilarning kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini oshiradimi yoki yo'qligini tekshiradi. Tadqiqot 8-sinf o'quvchilari ishtirokida so'rovga asoslangan usuldan foydalanildi. Dastlab, so'rovnoma so'zlashda

asosiy qiyinchiliklarni, jumladan, ikkilanish, cheklangan soʻz boyligi va past ishonchni aniqlash uchun oʻtkazildi. Soʻrov natijalariga koʻra maqsadli sinf faoliyati ishlab chiqildi va amalga oshirildi. Ular orasida rolli oʻyinlar va bahs-munozara mashgʻulotlari oʻrin olgan boʻlib, ular talabalarni mazmunli va real vaziyatlarda tildan faol foydalanishga undadi. Talabalarning nutq qobiliyatidagi oʻzgarishlarni kuzatish uchun tadbirlar maʼlum bir davrda amalga oshirildi.

Kalit soʻzlar: muloqot, nutq qobiliyatlari, ravonlik, real hayotiy vaziyatlar, qiyinchiliklar, oʻquvchilar, soʻrovnoma va intervyu, rolli oʻyin va bahs, rolli oʻyin va bahs, ravonlik, ikkilanish, uyatchanlik, tengdoshlar, oʻziga ishonch.

INTRODUCTION

Communication skills are essential to learning a language and to expressing ideas and information. That's why instructors should develop effective methods to enhance their learners' speaking skills.

Background. There have been numerous studies focusing on improving learners' speaking skills, as fluency is not simply about learning vocabulary and grammar, but about integrating that knowledge into one's thought process to communicate naturally. As Andrew Grogan explains, fluency is a gradual process that requires patience, practice, and perseverance. However, many learners face psychological barriers that hinder their ability to speak in an English classroom.¹ According to Juhana, psychological factors such as fear of making mistakes, shyness, anxiety, lack of confidence, and lack of motivation hinder students from speaking in English class. Those factors, such as fear of making mistakes, were often driven by their fear of being laughed at by their friends. The possible solution to overcome those psychological factors, most students believed that motivating them to be more confident to speak English is worth considering.² Similarly, Marriam Bashir, Muhammad Azeem, and Ashiq Hussain Dogar note that language learners are often too embarrassed or shy to speak when they do not understand others or when they realize they have not been understood.³ In addition, Svetlana Prodius points out that many people believe they need better materials or that the language itself is too difficult; however, the real issue is that studying builds theoretical knowledge, whereas

¹ Andrew Grogan October 14, 2024- "Why is it so hard to learn a language fluently?" – Medium <https://share.google/8sboKq9wDGGvsJ15d>

² Juhana 2012- "Psychological Factors That Hinder Students from Speaking in English Class" - Journal of Education and Practice <https://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/JEP/article/view/2887>

³ Marriam Bashir, Muhammad Azeem, and Ashiq Hussain Dogar January, 2011- "Factor Effecting Students' English Speaking Skills" https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228840274_Factor_Effecting_Students'_English_Speaking_Skills

speaking requires practical application. Reading improves reading, listening improves listening, and grammar drills improve test scores, but only speaking practice improves speaking, meaning that fluency cannot be achieved through textbooks alone.¹

Furthermore, as Khakimov Saminjon (December 24, 2025) explains, speaking is an active skill: while reading and listening allow time to think and process meaning, speaking demands the immediate selection of appropriate words, accurate grammar, and clear pronunciation. This time pressure makes speaking stressful for many learners, especially in classrooms that emphasize grammar rules and written exercises over real communicative practice; consequently, students often lack sufficient opportunities to use English in authentic conversations².

Aim. This research is conducted to identify practical solutions to the obstacles that prevent learners, particularly students in grades 8–10, from speaking English confidently in real-life situations. It also aims to explore effective and innovative methods for enhancing speaking skills. In addition, the study reviews previously applied approaches to improving speaking ability and seeks to discover new strategies for both teaching and learning speaking more consciously and effectively.

This research paper reveals a detailed look at the following objectives:

Figure 1.1. The objectives of research

¹ Svetlana Prodius November 8, 2025- “Why You Still Can't Speak Fluently (And What Actually Works)” <https://share.google/Zw9PT5GRh07adBSnT>

² Khakimov Saminjon December 24, 2025- “Why many English learners understand the language but cannot speak”. <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/70166>

16 pupils from 8-10 grades at 5 states at school No 33 in the Kosonsoy district, Namangan region.

The research based on students' fluency and the most effective ways to improve it was prepared according to the procedure used by Juhana. Traditionally, speaking has been assessed by measuring language competence. However, learners have been failing to use it in real-life situations, even though they can understand this language while listening and reading. To test our primary hypothesis on why learners struggle to use the language that they are learning, we conducted a questionnaire to able to gain information about the challenges that learners are facing in the learning process. The design was a mixed-method study that included peer work and role play, that are mixed to enhance speaking skills. Observations were conducted at school N_33, which is located in the Kosonsoy district, Namangan region. Criteria for selecting the subjects were as follows: the research was conducted among 8-10 grades, that are 16 students (7 girls, 9 boys)

A major advantage of peer work is that it can help learners to speak in English without hesitation and shyness, and role play is also a highly effective technique for improving speaking skills in language learning classrooms. They create a more interactive, engaging, and student-centered environment. Speaking skills is one of the four main language skills: listening, reading, writing, and speaking. It is the ability to express ideas, thoughts, and feelings clearly and effectively through spoken language. This research was conducted with 16 pupils (9 boys and 7 girls) at a local school that is located in the Kosonsoy district. The participants were selected randomly from the same grade. All of them were 13-14 years old, and their level of English was pre-intermediate. The data of the research consisted of a questionnaire and an interview. The questionnaire was designed to find challenges that learners face when they speak in English, while interview was used to identify learners' speaking ability and their level. The independent variable in this study was the use of role play and peer work tasks, and the dependent variable was students' speaking performance.

This research was conducted in several stages. When I went to school for a practicum for the first time, I observed many students who were struggling to use the language, so I decided to explore this problem and find solutions through research. First, the pupils completed a paper-based survey that included six questions to find out their problems. According to their results, hesitation, lack of confidence, and pronunciation were indicated as the biggest problems while speaking, and environmental factors like limited use of English outside the classroom block their skill.

According to the survey results, I first conducted interviews with the students to identify their outcomes. During this period, the problems they mentioned were observed. Based on these findings, I organized the lessons using peer work and role-play methods. This research lasted for two weeks. During this time, more speaking-based practical exercises were given in the lessons. At first, students talked with their classmates about topics they personally liked and found interesting. After that, the class was divided into two groups, and each time they were given relevant and familiar topics, followed by short debates. During these activities, students became highly engaged and spoke freely, especially during role play. The teacher was not in the main role but acted as a facilitator, which helped shift from a teacher-centered approach to a student-centered one, and their vocabulary was actively developed.

Figure 1.2. Applying debate and role play methods in the classroom

After the lessons, students were divided into groups of four, and they were given real-life situations to prepare at home and perform in class (such as situations at a shop, airport, or restaurant). Working with friends and performing role-plays was very

interesting and enjoyable for them. However, pupils faced some challenges in understanding the rules of debate and participating in it, so it was a bit hard to conduct a debate with them. To evaluate the results of the two-week study, students were given random questions and situations. The results showed that students were able to speak English fluently without hesitation or shyness.

Results. A questionnaire was conducted among 16 eighth-grade pupils, including 9 boys and 7 girls, in order to investigate their attitudes toward learning English and the challenges they face in speaking. The findings reveal that students show mixed levels of interest in learning the language. Only 37.5% of the pupils expressed clear interest, while a small proportion (6.25%) were not interested at all. However, the majority, accounting for 56.25%, reported a neutral attitude, which suggests that many learners lack strong motivation or engagement in the learning process.

Figure 2. The rate of pupils' interest for English

The data also highlights the main difficulties students encounter when speaking English. More than half of the participants (56.25%) identified hesitation as their biggest problem, indicating a lack of confidence during communication. In addition, 25% of the pupils reported limited vocabulary as a barrier, while 18.75% struggled with pronunciation. These findings suggest that psychological factors such as fear and hesitation play a more significant role than purely linguistic challenges.

Figure 3. The percentages of challenges learners can face with

Another important issue revealed by the questionnaire is the inability of students to use English in real-life situations. A large majority (81.25%) attributed this problem to the lack of an English-speaking environment. Only 6.25% considered insufficient vocabulary as the main reason, while 12.5% pointed to a lack of homework or practice. This clearly shows that the absence of real communication opportunities is the most critical factor limiting language use.

Figure 4. The reasons that why learners have difficulties while speaking

Furthermore, the results indicate that many students are not confident in expressing themselves in English, even among their classmates. While 31.25% of the pupils stated that they can express themselves, a slightly higher percentage (37.5%) reported that they cannot. Meanwhile, 31.25% remained neutral. This distribution demonstrates that a significant number of learners struggle with self-expression and confidence in speaking.

Figure 5. The rate of whether working with peers works or not

Regarding preferred learning methods, the majority of students (62.5%) believe that games are the most effective way to learn English. In contrast, 25% preferred imitation, while only 12.5% chose to practice with friends. This suggests that interactive and engaging activities play a crucial role in motivating learners and improving their language skills.

Figure 6. The methods that can help enhance speaking based on the learners reply

Finally, the questionnaire checked the level of students' active vocabulary. The results show that 62.5% of the pupils have less than 20% active vocabulary, while 25% reported having around 50%. Only 12.5% of students claimed that more than half of their vocabulary is active. This indicates that limited active vocabulary is a major factor affecting students' ability to communicate effectively.

Figure 7. The percentage of learners' vocabulary types (active, passive)

Discussion. The results of methods that I utilized during 2 weeks really assisted them to show their hidden knowledge in the real life. Role play and debate are more useful ways to enhance pupils' speaking skill and lose their shyness and hesitation as well as improve their topic - based vocabulary.

When role play was given as homework to pupils, they were so engaged and dived deeply into those situations were actual that they always come across, and they were not shy to speak in front of their peers with self- confidence, which was also one of the goals of this research. For example, a situation in the shop was given to one group, they created a mini-shop and half of that group were shop assistants, and the other were customers, while performing that, they used lots of words that are used in daily conversation.

During the lesson, common topics that were also appropriate to their level were given for organizing a debate. At first, they were highly engaged to this, because it was

a new and uncommon thing for them, and I explained how to do it. The sixteen pupils were divided into two groups and each group should speak about the advantages and disadvantages of cycling. They mentioned many good ideas, and because of the competition, they spoke freely and without any hesitation.

When it comes to the poor side of those methods, while conducting debates with pupils, they made extra noise and spoke without permission, even though I did not let, controlling them was a bit hard for me, and some pupils did not join to debate, because other pupils did not give them a chance to speak, even though I warned them. In addition, this research was conducted with a small group of 8 grade pupils from only a class as well as short duration of the research may not let to generate clear results. Therefore, future research should involve with much more learners and over a long period to better understand the impact of role play and debate on learners' speaking skills.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to analyze the problems that language learners face while speaking and to explore the role of role play and debate in improving their speaking performance. The findings showed that hesitation and a lack of lexical resources are the main factors affecting learners' ability to speak effectively. After organizing lessons that included debates on topics commonly relevant to students, as well as assigning role-play activities as homework with their peers, noticeable improvements were observed. According to the results, pupils became more engaged and spoke more freely and confidently. This was especially evident when they performed real-life situations, as they became deeply involved and worried less about making mistakes.

The study highlights the importance of integrating speaking activities into lessons and adopting more interactive teaching methods. It also emphasizes a shift from a teacher-centered approach to a student-centered one. In this approach, teachers no longer play a dominant role; instead, they act as facilitators, guides, and motivators. Overall, role play and debate are highly effective methods for teaching and improving speaking skills.

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